

Gender-Fairness and Linguistic Elegance: No Contradiction

Hans-Friedrich Witschel¹[0000–0002–8608–9039], Corina Masanti^{2,1}[0009–0002–4104–6315], and Kaspar Riesen²[0000–0002–9145–3157]

¹ Institute for Informations Systems, University of Appl. Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland, 4600 Olten, Switzerland,

`hansfriedrich.witschel@fhnw.ch`

² Institute of Computer Science, University of Bern, 3012 Bern, Switzerland, `{corina.masanti,kaspar.riesen}@unibe.ch`

Abstract. We study in how far the application of advanced techniques from the area of generative artificial intelligence can help mitigate gender bias in German text in a linguistically elegant way. For us, elegance refers to gender neutrality in an unobtrusive or unnoticeable way, e.g. by avoiding lengthy rewritings or the use of special characters like gender stars. Our results show that advanced prompting methods do indeed help to improve correctness and elegance, while still not delivering perfect results. To allow future work to address persisting shortcomings, we have performed an in-depth analysis and inductive coding of error categories which provide insights into common linguistic challenges around gender-neutral rewritings. We show in an exemplary way how finetuning and direct preference optimisation can help to address these problems.

Keywords: Gender bias correction · Large Language Models · Linguistic Challenges.

1 Introduction

The question of whether or not the use of gender-fair language should be promoted has led to considerable debates in society.

On the one hand, it has been empirically shown that generic masculine forms are in fact cognitively associated more frequently with male actors [14], that this leads to a smaller sense of identification in women [15] and provokes gender stereotypes and judgments in all humans [9]. Thus, there is strong evidence that the use of gender-fair language can have an impact on society and the empowerment of women [13].

On the other hand, criticism of gender-fair language adaptations persists, using a number of arguments, of which four prominent categories have been identified by [18]. Apart from categories that ultimately originate from sexism or denial of the above arguments, two categories refer to linguistic challenges that gender-fair language brings with it: firstly, some persons attempted to defend the linguistic status quo by referring to gender-neutral reformulations as difficult, awkward and/or unnecessary. Although studies have not shown negative

effects of using gender-fair language on text comprehensibility [7], test persons frequently found it hard “to get used to it” and often awkward. Secondly, there was concern that the use of certain gender-fair formulations might take attention away from the actual message to be conveyed.

While one may argue about these concerns, there are movements that try to take “linguistic concerns” about the potential awkwardness of gender-fair reformulations seriously and counter them by suggesting more “unobtrusive” or elegant ways of achieving gender-fairness (see e.g. [16] for German³).

We believe that preservation of linguistic elegance could be an important step towards raising the acceptance of gender-fair language and that technological advances may help society in achieving such elegance. Therefore, the goal of this paper is to investigate the feasibility of supporting “smart gendering”, i.e. the production of linguistically elegant gender-fair reformulations with methods of generative artificial intelligence, without producing incorrect language or changed semantics.

2 Related Work

In this section, we discuss related work in the areas of identifying gender bias in text, as well as strategies to mitigate it via (elegant) reformulations.

For the task of identifying gender-biased words or formulations, some simple approaches using lexicons of gender-biased words [8] have been proposed, together with linguistic rules to determine if masculine words refer to a female person or a mixed-gender group [4], i.e. whether they are instances of “generic masculine”.

The aim of such detection is usually to rewrite the gender-biased text. Consequently, there is abundant research investigating rewriting models – many of the corresponding approaches do this in an end-to-end approach. That is, the model is fed with some text (often a sentence) and asked to rewrite it in a gender-neutral way, without first detecting the presence and location of biased words or phrases in it. Some of these approaches use rules together with machine learning [17, 1], others rely exclusively on machine learning, by training sequence-to-sequence models [2].

One important challenge related to machine learning approaches is the need to have a large collection of pairs of gender-fair and gender-biased versions of a piece of text (e.g. sentences) as training data. To this end, lexicons and labeled datasets have been compiled [6]. To be able to work with larger amounts of text, several approaches rely on the automated creation of the above-mentioned sentence pairs [2, 1, 17]. For instance, Amrhein et al. [2] exploit the gender biases inherent in automated machine translation systems to create gender-biased versions of a gender-neutral sentence via translation into English (which is mostly gender-free) and back into the original language.

³ see also <https://geschicktgendern.de>

The advent of very large language models (LLMs) has led to the question in how far gender neutrality can be achieved using LLMs, thus avoiding the need to compile large specialised training corpora

To start with, there is an increasing number of studies that investigate the extent to which gender bias and stereotypes are present in LLM-generated text, see [11] for a recent survey. Largely, the results show that gender bias can be rather strong in LLM-generated texts [10].

Despite this fact, it has been discovered that biases can be reduced via instruction/prompting [5], as well as by controlling or providing appropriate linguistic context [19]. Thus, LLMs can be prompted to produce gender-neutral text, also when asked to reformulate gender-biased input text.

Because of the still existing imperfections of such prompting approaches, finetuning of LLMs has also been investigated, e.g. Bart and Leavy [3] use a finetuning approach to replace gender-biased English words with alternative ones.

So far, however, “elegant” ways of rewriting as introduced in [16] have received very little attention. One example of elegance refers to the avoidance of paired forms (i.e. enumerating male and female forms) which are tiresome and awkward to read [18], exclude non-binary persons and carry the risk of preserving biases via “male-firstness” [20].

Our contribution is threefold:

- We show that a higher quality of rewritings can be achieved via a two-step approach where an LLM first detects generic masculine words or phrases and then gets prompted to reformulate them
- We show how LLMs can be not only prompted but also finetuned to achieve elegance, in the sense that their rewritings avoid gender stars (or other special characters) as well as overly long constructions as far as possible, at the same time suppressing incorrect morphology or syntax and changed semantics
- We provide a qualitative analysis of challenges encountered when building such solutions and develop a coding scheme for quantifying the extent to which corresponding errors occur in the rewritings. This helps to better understand where improvements are still needed in future work.

3 Approach

Overall, the problem that we want to solve consists in receiving a piece of text in German language – usually a sentence – and rewriting it into a gender-neutral form by removing any generic masculine formulations and replacing them with elegant gender-neutral rewritings. This includes the possibility that no change is necessary.

We explicitly focus on the avoidance of generic masculine formulations, i.e. the use of words that imply a male referent where the gender of the referent is unknown or a group of persons with mixed gender.

3.1 Task Definition

More precisely, we need to define the notion of “elegance” which we equate with writing a text that does not look like it has been edited for gender-neutrality. To measure the extent to which this has been achieved, one can measure a) the length of the text (the shorter the better) and b) the lack of special characters such as “gender stars” (*).

Unfortunately, these two criteria can be in conflict with each other: often, gender stars can be avoided at the expense of making the text longer and vice versa. Sometimes, solutions exist that satisfy both criteria; if this is not the case, we will not prefer one of the criteria over the other since we believe that it is a matter of personal taste. We measure the length of a text in number of words, not characters. Since German can form compound words, using a compound (e.g. “Polizeileute” = police staff) instead of a shorter alternative non-compound (e.g. “Polizei” = “police”) will be penalized.

Thus, we have overall three goals to pursue: Given an input text, we want to have an output that is

1. Gender-neutral (goal 1)
2. Semantically as close as possible to the input sentence (goal 2) and
3. Linguistically as elegant as possible, according to our above definition of elegance (goal 3)

One can argue whether the output text should also be syntactically as close as possible to the input. We do not target this because gender-neutral alternatives can sometimes be syntactically very different from the original, yet semantically equivalent and linguistically elegant.

Of course, the semantic equivalence depends on the context and has to be judged individually. It is clear that stronger syntactic conversions also carry a larger risk of changing the semantics.

3.2 Overall Solution

For goals 2 and 3 above, it can greatly help an LLM to know which words in an input text are not gender-neutral. This can help to avoid changing parts of the text that are already gender-neutral and thus to reduce the risk of changing the semantics or introducing unnecessary changes that negatively affect the linguistic elegance.

This is the reason why we chose a two-step approach. In fact, when using our approach in practice, we imagine that users will first be presented with warnings that highlight words or phrases that are not gender-neutral, and only upon the user’s request will our second model be invoked – with the problematic words or phrases as an additional input – to re-write the text.

3.3 Detection

The general idea of our approach is to work with a dataset of limited size and create iterative improvements of an LLM-based detection and rewriting solu-

tion by performing in-depth error analyses and addressing the most commonly observed linguistic challenges through prompt improvements and finetuning.

We use the dataset provided by [4], originally a set of 238 newspaper articles from the 1990s where the many generic masculine forms have been manually annotated. The dataset is small, but allows for qualitative analyses because of its reliably tagged gender-biased forms. It consists of 4,055 sentences, of which 738 contain at least one gender-biased word or phrase⁴.

We experimented with different LLMs, prompts and chain-of-thought strategies, as well as finetuning. Each of our iterations was based on an error analysis performed on the previous round: because of the available ground truth, we were able to identify sentences that were incorrectly tagged by the current solution. We developed an inductive coding scheme to capture the underlying linguistic problems and then addressed the most prominent of these by refining instructions or chain-of-thought strategies in the prompt. For each iteration of prompt engineering, we sampled 200 sentences at random and performed the in-depth error analysis and coding on these. Besides the counts of errors in each inductively defined category, we also computed the overall recall, precision and F1 measure.

For finetuning, the approach was different: here, we selected sentences with common errors still present in the best prompt engineering iteration and mixed them with roughly the same number of sentences without gender bias. This can be regarded as a form of undersampling of the majority class – i.e. reducing the amount of training examples from the majority of gender-neutral sentences, thus making it more sensitive to gender bias. We deliberately trade a higher recall for potentially lower precision here since ignoring some “false alarms” is substantially less effort than manually detecting errors overlooked by the system. Finally, the finetuned model was again evaluated on 200 randomly selected sentences from the original corpus, ensuring that none of the sentences used in finetuning were used.

3.4 Rewriting

For rewriting experiments, the first author of this paper manually rewrote all 738 gender-biased sentences into a gender-neutral form. As we will see later, these rewrites may be challenged by other humans (e.g. a professional proofreader whom we involved), but do serve as a “ground truth” to which the machine-generated rewrites were compared. We then set aside a test set of 100 gender-biased sentences.

On another set of sentences, a zero-shot model was applied and the gender-biased word(s) or phrase(s) contained in each sentence were added to the prompt (see previous section). The authors of the paper then went through the result, comparing each rewriting proposed by the model to the human rewriting (ground truth). We inductively developed a coding scheme to describe the variety of errors or differences encountered during this comparison.

⁴ publicly available at <https://github.com/theodm/gender-assistenz>

Then, we went through all 100 sentences of our test set together with a proofreading expert and applied the coding scheme. It turned out that, while annotating, a common understanding of the meaning of codes first had to be developed – sometimes, the codes leave room for varied opinions when applied to tricky examples. However, the common understanding increased over time and an agreement for the coding of test sentences was reached in all cases.

In the following, the goal was *not* to construct a model that would not suffer from any of the weaknesses discovered when analysing the outputs of the baseline model. Rather, we wanted to find out whether a combined approach of finetuning and direct preference optimization (with our limited training data) would have a desired impact on results for an exemplary problem category (in our case the largest error category, see Section 4 below), i.e. avoiding an undesired behaviour while not introducing new problems.

We expect that, if this can be achieved, the approach can also be extended to the other problem categories – and can thus be tailored to the specific needs of a given context and involved stakeholders.

The procedure for creating the training set for finetuning and direct preference optimisation (DPO) [12] was as follows:

- From the 638 sentences that had not been used in the test set, 300 sentences were selected, run through the zero-shot model and then manually annotated by the primary author w.r.t. the largest error class (it must be noted here, again, that the primary author is not a professional in proofreading, thus it may be possible that a small portion of these annotations is not fully correct. However, we expect this problem to be negligible).
- This resulted in 69 sentences where the zero-shot model made that error
- Now, the strategy was to first finetune the baseline GPT-4o model, using 39 of these sentences (“Set 1”) and to then apply DPO using the remaining 30 sentences (“Set 2”)
- For finetuning, i.e. for all sentences in Set 1, the human reformulation of the sentence was provided as an example. For DPO, i.e. for all sentences in Set 2, the human reformulation was used as “preferred” variant, the output of the zero-shot model was used as “non-preferred”

Finally, the finetuned model was again applied to the test set and its output was coded using the coding scheme mentioned above. The same was done for two baseline models – one with a much simpler prompt and another one that was not even provided with the gender-biased words to avoid. The latter served as a check regarding the value of our two-step approach of first detecting gender-biased words and then avoiding them.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Detection

Table 1 shows the 5 iterations we performed to improve the detection of gender-biased words and phrases.

Iteration	LLM	Techniques
1	GPT 3.5	initial prompt
2	GPT 4	revised prompt based on error analysis, chain-of-thought
3	GPT 4	improved chain-of-thought based on error analysis
4	GPT 4o	same as round 3
5	GPT 4o	Finetuning

Table 1. Iterations for the detection of gender-biased forms

Error category	Count	Example extraction result
Extraction of gender-neutral word	38	Menschen (persons, gender-neutral)
Referent is a concrete male person	37	“... sagte Hans-Ulrich Klose, der Vorsitzende... ” (president)
Referent is inanimate	32	Konzerne (corporation)
Proper name	22	“...sagte Schäfer...” (used as proper noun, can also mean shepherd)

Table 2. Error categories (false positives) of gender bias detection, round 1

In Table 2, we see the most prominent categories of false positive errors. Although the model also produced some false negatives in Round 1, categorisation of these cases turned out much harder (i.e. there were less common patterns).

Figure 1 shows detection results for the 5 iterations in terms of precision, recall and F1 measure. We can observe that the value of F1 is constantly increasing, reaching 0.85 in iteration 5.

In the first 4 iterations, this improvement is mostly brought about by addressing the false positive error categories (see Table 2) and thus increasing precision (blue bars). At the same time, recall stays rather stable, mostly below 80% in these iterations. The notable increase of recall to 97% in iteration 5 is made possible only by finetuning. As mentioned before, recall is very important to proofreading use cases, therefore the model of iteration 5 is considered good whereas the previous ones hardly meet the requirements of such use cases.

Figure 2 shows the final version of the prompt used for the detection task, used in iterations 3, 4 and 5 (i.e. also in the finetuning). We can see how it enforces precision by pointing the LLM to cases that can lead to false positives, e.g. concrete male persons as referents or words that are already gender-neutral (i.e. do not have a feminine form). These clarifications were added as a result of understanding the common error categories, see again Table 2.

4.2 Rewriting

Our inductively created coding scheme (see Section 3.4) distinguishes between errors (or unacceptable changes), less elegant rewritings and “good” rewritings of different kinds. Errors can be as follows:

- **Not gender-neutral** (binary): the output text is still gender-biased

Fig. 1. Detection results per iteration

- **Incorrect** word or syntax (scale): producing a word or syntactical construction that is not linguistically correct where a code of 1 is used for words or constructions that are not strictly wrong, but very uncommon and a code of 2 for ones that are clearly incorrect. An example of code 1 would be to use “Fahrende” (roughly:driving persons) instead of “Fahrer” (driver), a code 2 example is to write “die Zeug*in” (the witness, but using only a feminine article with a gender-neutral noun).
- **Drift** (scale): this refers to a change in meaning that is caused by the rewriting – this can be very slight (code 1), medium (code 2) or strong (code 3). An example of code 3: using “Militärangehörige” (military staff, gender-neutral) instead of “Offiziere” (officers, generic masculine).

In terms of less elegant rewritings, we distinguish:

- **Shorter possible** (binary): the rewriting uses a phrasing that requires more words (including words that are part of compounds) than the human version.
- **Unnecessary gender star** (binary): the rewriting applies a “gender star”, i.e. an asterisk put between the masculine form and the female suffix (e.g. “Kellner*in” – where “Kellner” means waiter and “Kellnerin” waitress). The human version manages to avoid the gender star *without* being longer.

Finally, there are also several ways in which “good” rewritings can be coded:

- **Same as human** (binary)

Find non-gender-neutral words in the following text and return them.
 Proceed as follows:

1. first make a list of all the words that are most likely to be non-gender-inclusive, i.e. used in the 'generic masculine'.
2. then check whether these words are really used as generic masculine in the sentence or whether there is a feminine form for them at all.

List all words (separated by commas) that

- a) refer to persons and are actually used in the generic masculine and
- b) for which there is a feminine form or gender-appropriate alternative and
- c) which do not refer to specific male persons in the text

If there are no such words, output the sentence: 'The text is gender-neutral.'

Fig. 2. Final prompt used for detection of gender-biased words (English translation from German)

- **Good alternative rewriting** (scale): this can be coded as 1 (better than human), 2 (valid alternative) or 3 (different compromise). Code 1 became necessary since sometimes, the model’s suggestions were in fact better than what the human (the author) had thought of. Code 2 referred to situations where the model chose a different formulation, without violating the above elegance criteria and without being more or less elegant than the human. Code 3 refers to a situation where both the model and the human violated the above criteria of elegance, e.g. the model used a gender star where the human chose a longer formulation or vice versa.

Before we turn to the results, we present the two baselines which are using simpler prompts and, in case of what we termed the “Absolute Baseline”, no identification of gender-biased words in the input. Figure 3 shows all 3 prompts that were used by the two baselines and the zero-shot model.

<p>Absolute_Baseline</p> <p>You are an assistant who helps to convert sentences into a gender-neutral form. You will receive one sentence as input. Please rewrite the sentence in such a way that neutral words are avoided and the resulting sentence is thus formulated in gender-neutral language.</p> <p>Rewrite the sentence as little as possible and do not change its content.</p>	<p>Zero-shot</p> <p>You are an assistant who helps to convert sentences into a gender-appropriate form. You receive two inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. a sentence 2. avoid: one or more words from the sentence that are not gender-neutral, separated by commas <p>Please rewrite the sentence in such a way that the non-gender-appropriate words (see input 2, 'Avoid') are avoided. Rewrite the sentence as little as possible and do not change its content.</p> <p>Try the following approaches, in the order given:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If there is a gender-appropriate alternative without a gender asterisk or explicit combination of feminine and masculine forms (e.g. 'Kundschaft' as an alternative to 'Kunden'), then use this. Check whether the alternative is really gender-neutral and whether it essentially has the same meaning as the word to be avoided! - If no such alternative exists, rearrange the sentence (as little as possible) so that the non-gender-appropriate word can be avoided (e.g. instead of 'Museumsbesucher müssen...' write, 'Bitte achten Sie darauf...'). - If this doesn't work either, replace non-gender-inclusive words with a variant with a gender asterisk (*innen). - If this doesn't work either (usually due to umlauts, e.g. in 'Bauern'), then replace non-gender-inclusive words with a combination of feminine and masculine forms (e.g. 'Bäuerinnen und Bauern').
<p>Baseline</p> <p>You are an assistant who helps to convert sentences into a gender-appropriate form. You receive two inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. a sentence 2. avoid: one or more words from the sentence that are not gender-appropriate, separated by commas 3. Please rewrite the sentence so that the non-gender-inclusive words (see input 2, 'Avoid') are avoided and the resulting sentence is formulated in gender-inclusive language. Rewrite the sentence as little as possible and do not change its content. 	

Fig. 3. Prompts used for rewriting (English translation from German)

Since we want to analyse the extent to which finetuning and DPO can improve an advanced prompting strategy, we first coded the results obtained with

the zero-shot version, i.e. we applied the model to our test set of 100 sentences and applied the coding scheme with the help of a professional proofreader.

Figure 4 (a) shows the results. It should be noted here that the numbers do not add up to 100 since quite a few sentences of the test set contain more than one gender-biased word or phrase.

Fig. 4. Coding results for (a) zero-shot learning and (b) finetuning, using GPT-4o in both cases

We can observe that the largest type of error that the zero-shot model makes is semantic drift, i.e. changing the meaning of the input sentence. We therefore created another model by identifying further sentences where the zero-shot model led to semantic drift and used them for finetuning and DPO (see Section 3.4 above). The results are shown in Figure 4 (b). We can observe very clearly that semantic drift is reduced when applying the fine-tuned model. At the same time, the other types of unacceptable errors do not increase and – as a rather unexpected positive side-effect – problems with unnecessarily lengthy rewritings decrease from 18 to 6. What does increase is the use of unnecessary gender stars. This is not surprising since the human rewritings of sentences used for finetuning and DPO often resorted to the use of gender stars. The finetuned model delivers overall slightly more correct and elegant rewritings (green bars, 66 in total) than the zero-shot model (58 in total).

In summary, finetuning and DPO achieve an improvement, in the sense that the number of unacceptable errors, specifically concerning semantic drift, are reduced, with no negative side-effects regarding other unacceptable types of errors and with slight negative side-effects on elegance in terms of avoiding gender stars. One might say that the finetuned model “plays it safe” by using gender stars a little more often than would be necessary.

Finally, Figure 5 shows a comparison of high-level coding results for all models, including our two baselines. The absolute baseline includes an additional code for the unacceptable error of altering words or phrases that were not gender-biased (remember that the absolute baseline does not receive information about which words or phrases to bring into a gender-neutral form). This error occurs 19 times, showing that our two-step approach makes sense. This error category also explains why the total number of cases is higher for the absolute baseline.

Fig. 5. Summary of coding results for all models. Red bars represent unacceptable errors, orange ones stand for less elegant rewritings and green bars are correct and elegant rewritings

In summary, we see how the number of unacceptable errors decreases from top to bottom in Figure 5, showing that advanced prompting, finetuning and DPO help to mitigate problems while not (yet) achieving a perfect result.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

This paper discusses how rewriting of text can be achieved such that the output is not only gender-neutral and correct but also linguistically elegant. This is done in two steps, by first identifying gender-biased words and phrases and then directing an LLM toward the elimination of these using advanced prompting and finetuning. The results show that a higher quality of rewritings can be achieved – both in terms of minimisation of common errors and in terms of elegance – without notable side effects. In the course of our studies, we also developed a coding scheme for linguistic problems that occur in both steps which better helps to understand and quantify the obstacles that are still present when using LLMs for the production of gender-neutral text.

We believe that our in-depth analysis of error categories can help future work, both when building explicit solutions for removing gender bias and when improving LLMs in general. This can be done by addressing categories we did not focus on (i.e. other than semantic drift) and by studying these effects on larger sample sizes. In practice, the prompts presented in Figures 2 and 3 can be used easily by anyone to enhance communication in everyday life.

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